

11th Central European Congress on Food and Nutrition

CEFood Congress Book

**“Food, technology and nutrition for
healthy people in a healthy environment“**

Editors:

**Peter Raspor, Irena Vovk, Andrej Ovca,
Sonja Smole Možina, Bojan Butinar, Mojca Jevšnik**

Ljubljana, 2022

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Acknowledgment	1
TABLE OF CONTENTS	5
INTRODUCTORY	9
CEFOOD FROM SLOVENIA BACK TO SLOVENIA IN 20 YEARS	13
RECOGNIZED SLOVENIAN CONTRIBUTORS IN THE FOOD AREA	27
PLENARY LECTURES	39
KEYNOTE LECTURES	49
ORAL PRESENTATIONS	63
CE-I-FooDay – CENTRAL EUROPEAN INSPIRATION FOOD DAY	99
ROUNDTABLE: “Edible insects – Food of the future?”	113
WORLD CAFÉ ON FOOD SUPPLEMENTS	115
WORKSHOP: “Challenges for beer and wine in today's food world”	119
WORKSHOP: “Food and its safety in a fast changing world”	125

WORKSHOP: “Modern food: Local vs. global, traditional vs. innovative in the “healthy” perspective”	133
FLASH PRESENTATIONS – Young researchers	137
POSTERS	145
PROJECTS	291
SUPPORTERS OF THE CEFOOD 2022	309
CEFood 2022 CONGRESS COMMITTEES	317
Author INDEX	323
CEFood 2022 CONGRESS PROGRAM	325

P-85

PY-GC-MS APPLICATION FOR MICROPLASTICS IDENTIFICATION AND QUANTIFICATION IN WATER SAMPLES

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It is estimated that about 300 million tons of plastics is produced annually worldwide. Almost 9% (25 million tons) of the total amount ends up as post-consumer plastic waste, out of which it is estimated that 38% ends up in landfill. In the environment, plastics are transformed into microplastics (MPs, size range of 1 μm –5 mm) and nanoplastics (NPs, <1 μm) by weathering, UV radiation, and biological degradation. Fragmentation of plastics into smaller particles has adverse environmental and health effects. Characterization of MPs is of great importance as MPs are detected in terrestrial and marine environments. While the research on marine MP is more advanced, there are immense gaps of knowledge regarding freshwater MPs. Pyrolysis gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (Py-GC-MS) is a common technique used in polymer science. Although Py-GC-MS does not allow the determination of size and morphology of MPs, Py-GC-MS can be used for identification and quantification of commonly used polymers that make MPs or NPs, i.e. polyethylene - PE, polypropylene - PP, polystyrene - PS, polyvinyl chloride - PVC, polyamide - PA, polymethyl methacrylate - PMMA, Polycarbonate - PC, and polyethylene terephthalate - PET. There are scarce data related to the analysis of MPs in water by Py-GC-MS and this paper summarizes them. The total amount of PE, PP, PS, PVC, PA, PMMA, PC and PET in drinking water ranged from 6.1 to 93.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. In the effluent water of the wastewater treatment plant, the concentration of PS was 60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The most abundant polymers found in surface waters were PE, PP, and PS. Despite of advantages of Py-GC-MS, for full characterization of MPs new analytical tools and a combination of available technologies are needed to complement the respective limitations of each technique for reliable characterization (morphological, physical, chemical) and quantification of MPs.

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